

Alimuhammedova Khabiba Rustamovna
Lecturer, Department of Foreign Languages
Tashkent University of Information Technologies

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5971509>

SEMANTIC STRUCTURE OF THE CONCEPT OF HUMAN "BEHAVIOUR" IN ENGLISH

Abstract: *In this article, the place of the concept Human "Behaviour" in the system of concepts is examined, as well as the existing in modern linguistics approaches to determining their semantic structure, which are based on disagreements regarding the number and nature of semantic components.*

Key words: *concept, semantics, semantic structure, feature, component, behaviour.*

It is known that cultural and linguistic systems have significant differences, but there are also so-called "semantic and lexical universals", originating in the general conceptual foundations of human thinking, culture and language. Based on this feature of the BEHAVIOR concept, it would be appropriate to analyze it, first of all, in terms of cognitive research (for more details on the principles of cognitively oriented research in the field of linguistics, see [1])

Scientists of the semantic school (V.A. Vinogradov, E.S. Kubryakova, V.Z. Demyankov, A.A. Kibrik, I.M. Kobozeva, E.V. Rakhilina, etc.) understand the concept as a term that serves explanation of the mental or psychic resources of our consciousness and the information structure that reflects the knowledge and experience of a person. The Concise Dictionary of Cognitive Terms provides the following definition of the term: "A concept is an operational meaningful unit of memory, a mental lexicon, a conceptual system and language of the brain, the entire picture of the world reflected in the human psyche" [2].

The lexical material of natural languages, like any multiple object, was subjected to attempts at typological classification with the allocation of thematic and semantic groups of words of various parts of speech, many of which included in their semantics (expressed concepts) the idea of perception (observation), and therefore were not indifferent to observer.

Such linguistic empiricism confirms some theoretical positions of cognitive grammar, one of which can be formulated as follows: semantic significance cannot be reduced to an objective situation, since the processes and methods of semantization (conceptualization) are subjective, alternative and depend on the characteristics of perception.

Sensitivity to the idea of perception and the observer manifested itself in various contexts. Although the observer has traditionally been considered in terms of a fictitious actant that does not have a syntactic (surface) expression, its hidden, implicit presence in the semantics of the analyzed words was mandatory. It seems that the expansion of the

methodological "powers" of the observer to include the ability to function as a real, syntactically expressible actant

The familiarization of behavior is naturally combined with its axiological interpretation. Behavior evaluation is what transforms people's actions into behavior; evaluation is the main semantic characteristic of the studied vocabulary, which manifests the concept BEHAVIOR.

An analysis of the definitions and semantic interpretations of this name allows us to draw the following conclusions: the name conduct is clearly "narrower in semantics than the word behavior, which is natural, since it is just a synonym for the name of the concept under study, its use is associated with such contexts as the general style of behavior in general (not specific behavioral acts), a moral/ethical assessment arising from these two contexts, the possibility of a stylistic assessment of a given word as fairly bookish in comparison with the name behavior, cf. See also an example that indicates the existence of certain rules of behavior in society:

It may be that the England management themselves will have to draw up a code of conduct in order to keep everyone happy

There are a significant number of verbs in the language, the semantic structure of which includes the "behavior" component with various modal, axiological and emotive elements. As an example, we will cite several verbs that imply this concept, as evidenced by the presence in their interpretation of the components "behave, impress, manner". Behavioral "specificity" is expressed precisely in such verbs, which is difficult to trace in examples with the verbs behave and conduct, which have broad semantics. These are such verbs as, for example, show off, exhibit, flirt:

Show off – try to impress people by making a display of one's wealth, learning, abilities, etc. [2];

to behave in a way that is intended to attract people's attention and make them admire you; to show people something that you are very proud of so that they will admire it [3];

to behave in a way that is intended to attract attention or admiration, and that other people often find annoying [4];

to try to impress others by talking about your abilities, possessions, etc; to show people somebody/something that you are proud of [5].

In conclusion, a comparative analysis of the semantics of the verbs behave and conduct, including the study of definitions, statements and the contextual environment of statements, makes it possible to definitely name the verb behave as the central verbalizer of the concept under study. By for a number of reasons mentioned above, in particular, stylistic marking, a clear tendency to be used in a positive context, the conduct predicate plays a secondary role in this regard.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

1. Leontev D.A. Psixologiya smisla. M., 1999.

2. Kubryakova Ye.S., Demyankov V.Z., Pankras Yu.G., Luzina L.G. Kratkiy slovar kognitivnix terminov / otv. red. Ye.S. Kubryakova. M., 1996. S. 90.
3. <https://www.macmillandictionary.com/dictionary/british/show-off>
4. <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/show-off>
5. Stepanov Yu.S. Konstanti: Slovar russkoy kulturi. M., 2001. S. 43.
6. Popova Z.D., Sternin I.A. Ocherki po kognitivnoy lingvistike. Voronej, 2001.
7. Bolshoy tolkoviy slovar russkogo yazika / otv. red. S.A. Kuznesov. SPb., 2001. S. 850.
8. Shanskiy N.M., Ivanov V.V., Shanskaya T.V. Kratkiy etimologicheskiy slovar russkogo yazika. M., 1975. S. 77.
9. Karasik V.I. Yazikovoy krug: lichnost, konsepti, diskurs. M., 2004.